

Ethics in engineering - Involving students and assessing institutions

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Abstract

Ethics in engineering is (or must be) a topic included in the set of transversal competences included in every engineering degree. Notwithstanding, having time for including it in classroom sessions is not an easy task, as the technical contents usually have priority when programming the schedule of courses.

An activity has been designed to introduce the topic in engineering courses. The activity is designed looking for two outcomes. On the one side, to make students aware of the ethical derivations of real-life situations related with the engineering profession. On the other hand, to know, from the students' point of view, the degree of implication of institutions in the inclusion of development of these type of competences in engineering studies.

The results of the study state that, while students agree with the relevance of having this topic included in the program, there is a lack of including ethics and social implications of the engineering profession in the curriculum.

Keywords: Education for sustainability; Ethics in engineering.

1 Introduction

Ethics in engineering is (or must be) a topic included in the set of transversal competences involved in every engineering degree. This is not a new topic, as there are lots of references about the social implications of engineering, spread over all the history of engineering itself. Just to highlight some of these references, I would like to mention some quotes:

- 'What the engineer is as a man is more important than what he is as an engineer', (Curtis, 1950).
- 'Engineers should realize that they do not practice their craft in a social vacuum', (Hirsh, 1995).
- 'What we do as engineers and why we do it, is based on our underlying values. However, rarely in engineering education is any consideration taken of our values, what they are and where they come from', (Nahar et al., 2009).
- 'Students as well as engineers need to recognize their own values and perspectives and what influences their point of view when they make scientific and engineering judgements', (Nahar et al., 2009).
- We may also include ethical considerations related with how COVID-19 has affected the researching, teaching and learning processes: 'Academia must foster a culture of care, help us refocus on what is most important, and redefine excellence in teaching and research' (Corbera et al., 2020).

Notwithstanding, having time for including it in classroom sessions is not always easy, as the technical contents usually have priority when programming the schedule of courses. But is important to take into account that students themselves are demanding having ethical and social issues included in their learning framework, as can be derive, as one clear example, from the outcomes of the meeting of the Board of European Students of Technology (BEST) symposium on education (BEST, 2006), in which the idea of having a course on ethics was supported by all the participants:

- The necessity of ethics in the engineering education was corroborated by the problems faced by engineers. They will be critical about all the information they will receive. Also they will be more confident when standing up for their own opinion, resisting outer pressure if needed. The critical thinking will be raised with a background on ethics that the engineers will have with this kind of courses. Thus, in everyday situations, the dilemmas will be solved in a better way and the long-term consequences of engineering discoveries will be more carefully evaluated.

- Ethics also have an important role on the gaps that there are inevitably in laws and involve the responsibility of communicating with the society, of presenting, objectively, one person's own work.
- Big need exist for engineers to understand ethical issues that will occur during their carrier, especially as engineers are the ones making the discoveries and they need to stimulate the consequences of those. Engineers have to stand up for their positions in ethically questionable cases.

Another interesting outcome of the BEST meeting was the definition of the role of the person in charge of ethics training, joining the practical and theoretical points of view, considering two different models:

- The person should have not just theoretical knowledge but also a practical background, the person should have experience as working as an engineer or as an option, special training on ethics.
- Cooperation among two persons: engineer who will be practical and philosopher who will be theoretical.

In the particular case of the Sound and Image in Telecommunication Engineering (SITE) degree in the University of Alicante, the general objectives of the program include some specific references to the topic:

- General aim (#4): The ability to solve problems and take decisions with initiative and creativity, and to communicate and transmit knowledge, skills and expertise, adhering at all times to the ethical and professional guidelines applicable to Technical Telecommunications Engineering.
- General aim (#7): The capacity to analyse and assess the social and environmental impact of technical solutions.
- Transversal competence (CT3): Students should have the ability to gather and interpret relevant data (normally within their field of study) to give opinions that include a reflection on important, social, scientific, ethical matters, etc.
- Specific competence (C6): Capacity to conceive, deploy, organise and manage telecommunications networks, systems, services and infrastructures in residential (home, urban and digital communities), business and institutional contexts, as well as understanding their economic and social impact.

But, when taking a detailed reading to the syllabus there is no real inclusion of these goals in any of the degree courses. One of the few exceptions is the 4th year course Advanced Audio-visual Systems that includes the goal '*Students will be concerned about the challenges and social implications of the engineering work*'. Besides, the fact of finding a goal about the topic does not necessarily implies that the problem is considered in the course development.

With these ideas in mind, an activity was designed to make students reflect about the social and ethical implications of engineering that can be included at any level taking a gap between 1,5 and 3 hours of class time. The activity pursues a double objective, on the one hand, to include the reflection about the topic with the students in an explicit way and, on the other hand, to collect information about students' opinion to analyse if issues related to engineering values are (or not) taken into account in the SITE (or any other) degree.

A pilot study was done in 2011 (Romá, 2012) to have a picture about students' opinion about this topic and its results will be used as a reference for the analysis of the results In the present work.

2 Goals

Project goals can be summarized in a series of specific objectives:

- Design and implementation of activities to work in an explicit way general aims #4 and #7 and competencies CT3 and C6 as stated in the SITE degree program.
- Evaluation of SITE degree students' opinion about the necessity of considering the social derivations of the engineering work as a part of their curriculum.
- Assess if general aims #4 and #7 and competences CT3 and C6 are treated in the degree and evaluate possible changes respect the previous study from 2011

3 Method

Even though the activity can be implemented without restrictions with students of any course and any age, in order to fulfil with the last goal, the results that will be presented correspond with the experience carried out with last year students. The data has been collected from almost 40 students enrolled in the course Advanced Audio-visual Systems during the first semester of the 2019-20 academic year.

After running the activity, the main information source comes from a questionnaire complimented as an outcome of the reflection stage.

The most useful tool that has been considered is to face students with realistic situations they would find in their working environment, stimulating, as much as possible, confronted positions. To put these situations into context, the examples have been selected taking into account their relationship with the audio-visual engineering framework.

To ensure a proper debate, the activity is planned as a role game, so students have to take a clear position supporting or refusing the facts presented. It is, obviously, important, that the situations presented to the students facilitate the search of arguments from both points of view. Figure 1 shows the front slide used to present the activity. The idea of the pros and cons of technology or engineering underlying the roles assignment is clearly shown in the image.

Figure 1. Front slide of the presentation of the activity.

Ideally, after a first stage of 'white or black' positions the debate will show that a reflexive decision making process is a complex task that will lead to many derivatives not easy to handle and usually out of control. The background of some of the topics presented are:

- Production deallocation and the debate between final product price vs real production cost and employment generation in the production country vs labour conditions.
- Lack of funds for research projects vs having research funds from arms industry.
- Reduction of manufacturing or maintenance costs of vehicles vs environmental implications.

Students will have a specific and detailed situation to distribute roles related with each one of the mentioned situations.

3.1 Debate stage

As an introduction to the topic, students will first have to answer, individually and in a personal and honest way, to the question 'why did you decided to become an engineering student?'. After that, the activity is structured as follows;

- A case and a role (supporting or refusing the case) are assigned randomly to each one of the students. Students will have to find, in a personal and honest way, their starting point of view about the designated case.
- Groups are arranged including all the students with the same designated case and role to prepare a list of arguments to support their designated role.
- Rearrangement of groups with students with both roles of the same case for the debate. A list of the most relevant aspects will be prepared after the debate.
- Students join the working teams they use in the course and share debates outcomes. Each group is asked to think about a couple of real life decision making situations in which the ethical background is relevant. Finally they have to answer to the questions 'has this task been useful for you?' and 'have you obtained any new point of view?'

3.2 Reflection stage

After the debate activity, students are asked to answer, individually, a series of reflection questions:

- Prepare a list of aspects related with the topic 'ethics in engineering' that, according to your opinion, should be included in engineering degrees.
- Classify each ones of those aspects in the following categories: 'compulsory', 'important' (but not compulsory), 'expendable'.
- Grade in a 0-3 scale your opinion about the level of inclusion of each one of the aspects in the SITE degree (without taking into account this activity): 0 – not treated, 1 – marginally treated, 2 – treated in an insufficient way, 3 – treated in a sufficient way.

4 Results

This section includes two different aspects. On the one side, some considerations derived from the observation of the debates dynamics. On the other side, the analysis of the outcomes from the questions students answer in the reflection stage.

While all the groups are in the debate stage, it is interesting that the facilitator joins every group to provide new arguments if the debate is in stand-by and to gather information about debate dynamics in each one of the cases. It is remarkable that, in all the cases, as the starting point is well defined with black and white positions, the debates start vividly. As the students delve deeper in their topics they are aware that, in real life situations, the amount of derivatives is so big that having a clear position is not an easy task. Some of the students' most remarkable comments sate the relevance of broadening their own initial point of view or their astonishment when the economic approach is considered to be the only or most relevant one.

An interesting aspect of the results appears when analysing the real-life situations proposed by the students in which the ethical background is relevant. These examples generate a vision of the topics that are interesting for them and can be used as cases in future editions of the activity. The most significant aspects are:

- Robotics and its effect in employment.
- Autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence systems involved in decision making processes.
- Genetic engineering and dilemma between ethics and health.
- Inequity in labour relationships due to, among others, gender or raze reasons.
- Duality between development and environment.

Regarding students' opinion about the relevant aspects that may be included in the syllabus, the number of different ones has been high. All the mentioned items have been categorized in groups including similar

elements for the analysis. Just to make easy the comparison with the results from the pilot study in 2011, in this paper the same six categories are going to be used, even though a more detailed study have been done using specific categories that are more consistent whit the aspects obtained in 2019. Table 1 collects the number of mentions of each category in % obtained in 2011 and 2019 and also the deviation between the two sets of data. As not all the different topics can be clearly included in one of the defined categories, a seventh category includes the topics that cannot be included in the previous ones.

Table 1. Number of mentions of the most remarkable aspects highlighted by the students.

Topic	2011 (%)	2019 (%)
1 Acting according personal principles	24	19 (-5)
2 Social and environmental effects of own job	21	32 (+11)
3 Personal attitude (confident, personality, effort, ...)	16	11 (-5)
4 Fair labour conditions / work intrusion	12	5 (-7)
5 Economic considerations	9	1 (-8)
6 Professionalism	9	12 (+3)
7 Another not classified aspects	9	20 (+11)

It is remarkable the increase in the 'social and environmental effects' category and the reduction in the economic consideration.

As expected, using the categories that were designed in the pilot study and not for the present one, there has been an increase in the not classified category.

Figure 2 summarizes students' opinion about the average value of the relevance index of each one of the categories listed in Table 1 (solid lines), where the 0-2 scale represents 'expendable', 'important' (but not compulsory) and 'compulsory'. The dashed lines represent the average value of the perceive level of inclusion of each category in the SITE degree. The 0-3 scale represents: 0 – not treated, 1 – marginally treated, 2 – treated in an insufficient way, 3 – treated in a sufficient way.

Figure 2. Summary of students' opinion about relevance index (solid) and inclusion index (dashed) for the topics included in Table 1 for 2011 (black) and 2019 (blue).

Even though there is a slight difference in the relevance index between the two sets of data, this is due to the use of the same categories in the analysis and leads to non-significant results. The average relevance index

slightly decreases from 1.6 to 1.4 in the 0-2 scale, when the same categories is used in both data series. Comparing the relevance index using the categories designed for 2019, the obtained average value is 1.7.

The bad news come from the inclusion index results. This index indicates students' perception of the inclusion of each one of the topics without taking into account the presented activity. As this activity is performed in the first semester of a 4th year course, in almost 10 years gap there is not a perceived difference, and the index remains in very low levels. The average value of the inclusion index varies from 0.7 in 2011 to 0.5 in 2019 in a 0-3 scale, meaning that the overall result fits between not or marginally treated.

Being aware that the obtained values do not have real statistical significance, the clear outcome is that there is a remarkable gap between the need of having ethical related concepts and the inclusion of those concepts in the SITE degree. In the actual situation, that have been static over the years, the inclusion of ethics in engineering is only supported by individual interests without real implication of author's institution.

5 Conclusion

An activity has been designed to introduce the topic of 'challenges and social implications of the engineering work' that can be carried on in any engineering course, taking between 1.5 and 3 hours.

Students reaction to this proposal is very positive and it expands their vision about the conscious decision making process.

Comparing the results with those obtained in the pilot study, the interest and demand of this topic from the students is maintained but there is a remarkable difference between their demand and their perception of the inclusion of the topic in the degree.

6 References

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